

Synthesis of Coumaryl-4-acetic Acid.

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4-Methyl-coumarin being required in connection with another problem, attention was directed to its preparation. The substituted coumaryl-4-acetic acids, as a class, lose carbon dioxide when heated (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1806; Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 278). It was thought that the unsubstituted acid would give the desired 4-methyl-coumarin. Reference to the literature showed that the unsubstituted acid was not known to exist.

This led me to attempt the synthesis afresh, with the result that coumaryl-4-acetic acid can be prepared easily, the procedure is making use of the general method laid down by Dey and Row (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 112) as follows:—A sulphuric acid solution of acetone-dicarboxylic acid is prepared by mixing ten parts of citric acid with thirty parts of concentrated sulphuric acid and warming on the water-bath till the evolution of carbon monoxide ceases. On cooling, four parts of phenol followed by ten parts of sulphuric acid are slowly added with shaking and the reaction mixture is allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature (25°) for twenty-four hours. It is then poured into cold water and thoroughly extracted with ether. The acid is removed from the ethereal extract by alkali and is precipitated by dilute sulphuric acid. The yield of the crude acid amounts to 15 parts for 100 parts of phenol. The acid is purified by recrystallisation from water till it melts at 170° with decomposition. (Found: C, 64·5; H, 4·0. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires C, 64·7; H, 3·9 per cent. Neutralisation equivalent, 203·4. A monobasic acid $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires 204).

The acid when heated slightly over its melting temperature and kept at that point for some time, lost carbon dioxide and gave a liquid which solidified on cooling. This on recrystallising from water or alcohol, was identified with 4-methyl-coumarin both by direct comparison and through its bromo-derivative. These facts are quite in agreement with a coumaryl-4-acetic acid constitution for the new acid.

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